

Cardioversion for atrial fibrillation during pregnancy

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ABSTRACT Atrial fibrillation during pregnancy is a rare condition and often occurs in patients with underlying heart disease. The management of AF during pregnancy includes both electrical and pharmacological cardioversion to prevent recurrence and stroke. In recent years, few studies have been discussed the proper management of AF in pregnancy. This literature highlights both pharmacological and electrical cardioversion of atrial fibrillation during pregnancy.

KEYWORDS Atrial fibrillation (AF), cardioversion, pregnancy

Introduction

Atrial fibrillation is the most common chaotic cardiac rhythm abnormality affecting the activation of the atria. Cardioversion is needed to convert atrial fibrillation to sinus rhythm. AF during pregnancy is rare and often occurs in patients with underlying heart disease. Physiologic changes in pregnancy can predispose women to cardiac arrhythmias [1]. The management of AF during pregnancy includes electrical cardioversion followed by pharmacological cardioversion to prevent recurrence and stroke. AF, if not treated well, increased mortality and morbidity risk in both mother and fetus. Patient preference needs to be taken into consideration when choosing between electrical and pharmacologic conversion [2]. In recent years, few studies have been discussed the proper management of AF in pregnancy. There is a lack of published articles reporting the cardioversion of AF in pregnant women. Although the rarity of AF during gestation, it's essential to have available literature to enrich the current scientific knowledge of this condition. Our literature was prepared to help doctors whenever there is a rare case of AF in pregnancy. This review highlights both pharmacological and electrical cardioversion of atrial fibrillation during pregnancy. AF in pregnancy without any underlying heart disease is still a rare condition. We wished to amplify the literature on the cardioversion during pregnancy.

Search strategy

We searched for relevant studies published between 1965 to 2018 investigating arrhythmias during pregnancy, using MEDLINE, PubMed, the Google Scholar, the Cochrane register and Embase databases. These articles were retrieved by employing the terms "cardioversion" and "atrial fibrillation" and "pregnancy". The references list of case reports and review articles of atrial fibrillation was also searched with no language restriction.

Cardiovascular changes during pregnancy

Pregnancy is associated with significant anatomical and physiological changes in the cardiovascular system. The pregnant mother body adapts with metabolic changes to ensure uteroplacental circulation for fetal development [3]. During pregnancy, the cardiac output increases from the beginning of the first semester into the second trimester. Ducas et al. stated in a comparative study of 34 pregnant women that the cardiac output, the left ventricular end-diastolic volume, and the left ventricular mass increased during pregnancy [4]. The systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, and mean arterial pressure both decrease during pregnancy. A longitudinal cohort study conducted by Grindheim et al. has shown a decrease in BP during pregnancy [5]. The rises of cardiac output are associated with rises in heart rate and stroke volume. During normal gestation, heart rate increases progressively by 10 to 20 bpm. Some studies found that the overall change in heart rate represents 20% to 25% increase over baseline [6, 7]. Unlike many of the prior cardiovascular changes, the contractility of the heart during gestation does not differ from the normal adult. The myocardial contractility left, and right ventricular ejection fractions do not change during pregnancy stated by Poppas et al. [8]. The plasma volume, red blood cell mass, and total blood significantly increase during pregnancy [9, 10]. The mean circulatory filling pressure is also elevated in gestation, but the resistance to

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venous return is significantly reduced [11]. Arterial compliance also changes dramatically during normal gestation. Thus, both steady and pulsatile afterload decreases occur during pregnancy. Normal pregnancy is accompanied by multiple cardiovascular changes that can lead to arrhythmogenesis.

AF in pregnancy

Although AF is the most common sustained tachyarrhythmia, its incidence in pregnancy is relatively rare. AF may manifest for the first time and become more frequent during gestation, especially in women with congenital heart disease and in older women [12, 13]. In pregnant women, AF is associated with increased mortality risk and can lead to fatal hemodynamic compromise for the mother and fetus. Vaibhav et al. demonstrated this maternal mortality risk, [odds ratio (OR) 13.13, 95% CI 7.77-22.21; $P < 0.0001$], in a large descriptive observational analysis of pregnancy-related hospitalizations study [14]. AF in the gestation state can represent a benign, new onset lone AF or can manifest with structural heart disease. Sarah White et al. report a case of a 40-year-old G2 P1 female with 23-week twin gestation and a new-onset AF [15]. In the last few decades, more studies reported a series of cases of AF in pregnancy [16, 17, & 18].

The general assessment of AF in pregnant women should include an ECG, electrolytes, urine drug screen, a transthoracic echocardiogram (TTE) and thyroid studies. On ECG, AF is characterized by the absence of P waves, and the rapid fibrillatory waves that vary in shape, amplitude and timing associated with an irregular ventricular response [19]. In the pregnancy state, AF may manifest as acute dyspnea, palpitations, and chest pain. Viswajit Reddy Anugu et al. lately reported a case of a 30-year-old woman with 34 weeks gestation (gravida 3, para 0-0-2-0) who presents acute onset dyspnea, palpitations, and chest tightness, and whom the ECG showed AF with rapid ventricular response (160 bpm) [20]. Cardioversion should be performed to convert AF to sinus rhythm, and it should generally be preceded by anticoagulation therapy.

Cardioversion in pregnancy

The management of AF includes rate control, rhythm control, and prevention of thromboembolism. In pregnant women, AF management should be the same with faster intervention. The medication should be used with cautions to avoid harm to the fetus. Electrical cardioversion is safe during pregnancy. Synchronized electrical cardioversion is recommended whenever ongoing AF is hemodynamically unstable or a considerable risk for the fetus or the mother [21]. Cardioversion should be preceded by anticoagulation therapy [22]. Intravenous beta-blockers are recommended for rate control.

In hemodynamically stable patients or without any structural heart disease, delivery of intravenous beta-blockers may be considered for termination of AF [23, 24]. However, in patients with persistent AF, electrical cardioversion should be performed to convert AF to normal sinus rhythm, to avoid fetal harm by the side effects of the beta-blockers. Most of the antiarrhythmic drugs cross the placenta. The exposure to these drugs during pregnancy increases the risks of malformations of the fetus.

Electrical cardioversion up to 400 J can be performed if the risk of AF is considered high for both mother and fetus. It is safe to perform synchronized electrical cardioversion at all stages of pregnancy [25] (Class I level C recommendation). Cardioversion should be performed along with continuous fetal

monitoring [26]. Sauv N et al. reported recently a case-series showing 16 registry cases followed by the high rate of spontaneous cardioversion (in 81% of AF episodes) [27]. Synchronized cardioversion should be carried out safely during monitoring of maternal and fetal ECG. Electrical cardioversion is necessary for all hemodynamically unstable pregnant women and persistent AF [28].

Anticoagulation in pregnancy

To prevent thromboembolic and bleeding events, cardioversion requires prior anticoagulation therapy. Anticoagulation in pregnancy is more complex and should be considered in all patients except pregnant women with low thromboembolic risk or lone AF [29]. Low doses should be given for short periods. Heparin does not cross the placenta and may cause osteoporosis if given in high doses. Heparin should be given in the first semester and the last month of pregnancy. Although Warfarin may be associated with embryopathy and CNS abnormalities, it is safe during the remaining periods of gestation. Warfarin should be discontinued just before delivery [30]. Anticoagulation therapy in pregnancy should be continued at least for four weeks after cardioversion [31, 32]. If the bleeding risk is low then anticoagulation is not required; especially when sinus rhythm is restored in the first 48 hours of AF [33, 34, & 35].

Catheter ablation and pregnancy

In general, catheter ablation should be considered in persistent tachyarrhythmia, and need to be postponed to the second trimester of pregnancy [36]. The European Society of Cardiology recommends that the ablation should be performed using non-fluoroscopic electroanatomical mapping. Continuous fetal monitoring should be considered, and the patient should be positioned in the left lateral tilt position. The procedure needs to be performed at an experienced centre with the catheter navigation system. There are limited data concerning the ablation of AF in pregnancy obviously because of its rarity. In 1992, Dras D et al. reported an example case of radiofrequency ablation of atrioventricular conduction in five months pregnant women who had hypertrophic cardiomyopathy [37]. In other severe tachyarrhythmias, catheter ablation can also be performed in the second trimester of pregnancy. In recently published articles, Chen G. et al. [38] reported a catheter ablation successfully during pregnancy. The big challenge of this procedure is the risks of radiation of both maternal and fetal. Current guidelines support catheter ablation in poorly tolerated SVT, VT, [39] and drug refractory as class II and level of evidence B.

Complications

AF is associated with a higher risk of stroke. The hypercoagulable state of pregnancy [40] can predispose pregnant women with AF to an increased risk of thromboembolic complications [41, 42]. Although most of the studies investigating arrhythmias in non-pregnant women have associated AF with the risk of stroke, the extent of this risk is unknown during pregnancy [43]. The mechanism of AF associated with obstetric complications is also unknown [44]. However, Ming-Sum Lee et al. lately observed obstetric complications in 21.7% of cases of AF, in a retrospective, population-based study [45]. The fetus may suffer adverse effects of the treatment (fetal growth and development).

Key recommendations for arrhythmia cardioversion during pregnancy:

Arrhythmias	Recommendations	Class/ Levels	Ref
VF, VT, Cardiac arrest	The patient should be defibrillated with biphasic shock energy of 120 to 200 J with a subsequent escalation of energy output if the first shock is not effective and the device allows this option	I/B	[46] [47]
SVT, AF, AT	Immediate electrical cardioversion is recommended for any tachycardia with hemodynamic instability and for AF.	I/C	[22]
AT, SVT	Beta-selective blockers are recommended for rate control.	I/C	[22]
VF=ventricular fibrillation, VT=ventricular tachycardia, SVT=supraventricular tachycardia, AT=atrial tachycardia, AF= atrial fibrillation.			

Conclusion

AF is a rare condition during pregnancy. Factors such as age, congenital heart disease increase the risk of having AF during gestation. Obstetric complications are infrequent. However, when it appears in pregnant women, AF needs to be converted into normal sinus rhythm very quickly. We advise teamwork of a cardiologist and an obstetrician for the management of AF during pregnancy. Electrical or pharmacological cardioversion should be done according to the hemodynamically conditions. More population-based studies are needed to estimate the prevalence of AF in pregnancy and to adequately deal with this condition if it happened.

Competing Interests

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References

- DiCarlo-Meacham A, Dahlke J. Atrial fibrillation in pregnancy. *Obstet Gynecol.* 2011 Feb; 117 (2 Pt 2): 489-92.
- Vincenza Snow; Kevin B. Weiss; Michael LeFevre; Robert McNamara; Eric Bass; Lee A. Green; Keith Michl; Douglas K. Owens; Jeffrey Susman; Deborah I. Allen; Christel Mottur-Pilson; and the Joint AAFP/ACP Panel on Atrial Fibrillation. Management of Newly Detected Atrial Fibrillation: A Clinical Practice Guideline from the American Academy of Family Physicians and the American College of Physicians. *Ann Intern Med.* 2003; 139 (12):1009-1017.
- Monika Sanghavi and John D. Rutherford. Cardiovascular physiology of pregnancy. *Circulation.* 2014; 130: 1003–1008.
- Ducas RA, Elliott JE, Melnyk SF, Premecz S, daSilva M, Cleverley K, Wtorek P, Mackenzie GS, Helewa ME, Jassal DS. Cardiovascular magnetic resonance in pregnancy: insights from the Cardiac Hemodynamic Imaging and Remodeling in Pregnancy (CHIRP) study. *J Cardiovasc Magn Reson.* 2014; 16:1.
- Grindheim G, Estensen ME, Langesaeter E, Rosseland LA, Toska K. Changes in blood pressure during healthy pregnancy: a longitudinal cohort study. *J Hypertens.* 2012; 30:342–350.
- Mahendru AA, Everett TR, Wilkinson IB, Lees CC, McEniery CM. A longitudinal study of maternal cardiovascular function from preconception to the postpartum period. *J Hypertens.* 2014; 32: 849–856.
- Clapp JF 3rd, Capeless E. Cardiovascular function before, during, and after the first and subsequent pregnancies. *Am J Cardiol.* 1997; 80: 1469–1473.
- Poppas A, Shroff SG, Korcarz CE, Hibbard JU, Berger DS, Lindheimer MD, Lang RM. Serial assessment of the cardiovascular system in normal pregnancy: role of arterial compliance and pulsatile arterial load. *Circulation.* 1997; 95:2407–2415.
- Pritchard JA. Changes in the blood volume during pregnancy and delivery. *Anesthesiology.* 1965; 26: 393–399.
- Chesley LC. Plasma and red cell volumes during pregnancy. *Am J Obstet Gynecol.* 1972; 112:440–450.
- Michael E. Hall, Eric M. George, and Joey P. Granger. The heart during pregnancy. *Rev Esp Cardiol.* 2011 Nov; 64(11): 1045–1050.
- Opotowsky AR, Siddiqi OK, D'Souza B, Webb GD, Fernandes SM, Landzberg MJ. Maternal cardiovascular events during childbirth among women with congenital heart disease. *Heart.* 2012 Jan; 98(2):145-51.
- Alan D. Enriquez, Katherine E. Economy, and Usha B. Tedrow. Contemporary Management of Arrhythmias during Pregnancy. *Circulation: Arrhythmia and Electrophysiology.* 2014; 7: 961–967.

14. Vaidya VR, Arora S, Patel N, Badheka AO, Patel N, Agnihotri K, Billimoria Z, Turakhia MP, Friedman PA, Madhavan M, Kapa S, Noseworthy PA, Cha YM, Gersh B, Asirvatham SJ, Deshmukh AJ. Burden of Arrhythmia in Pregnancy. *Circulation*. 2017 Feb 7; 135(6):619-621.
15. Sarah White, Janna Welch, and Lawrence H. Brown. The Unexpected Pitter Patter: New-Onset Atrial Fibrillation in Pregnancy. *Case Rep Emerg Med*. 2015; 2015: 318645.
16. Carson MP, Fisher AJ, Scorza WE. Atrial fibrillation in pregnancy associated with oral terbutaline. *Obstet Gynecol*. 2002 Nov; 100 (5 Pt 2):1096-7.
17. Chia-Hui Lin, Chien-Nan Lee. Atrial fibrillation with rapid ventricular response in pregnancy. *Taiwan J Obstet Gynecol* September 2008 Vol 47 No 3.
18. Sengheiser CJ, Channer KC. Recurrent atrial flutter and fibrillation in pregnancy. *BMJ Case Rep*. 2011 Jun 3; 2011.
19. Haissaguerre M, Jais P, Shah DC, et al. Spontaneous initiation of atrial fibrillation by ectopic beats originating in the pulmonary veins. *N Engl J Med*. 1998; 339:659-666.
20. Viswajit Reddy Anugu, Nikhil Nalluri, Deepak Asti, Sainath Gaddam, Thomas Vazzana, and James Lafferty. New-onset lone atrial fibrillation in pregnancy. *Ther Adv Cardiovasc Dis*. 2016 Aug; 10(4): 274-276.
21. Kirchhof P, Benussi S, Kotecha D, Ahlsson A, Atar D, Casadei B, Castella M, Diener HC, Heidbuchel H, Hendriks J, Hindricks G, Manolis AS, Oldgren J, Popescu BA, Schotten U, Van Putte B, Vardas P. 2016 ESC guidelines for the management of atrial fibrillation developed in collaboration with EACTS. *Eur Heart J* 2016; 37: 2893-2962.
22. Vera Regitz, Zagrosek Jolien W Roos, Hesselink Johann Bauersachs, Carina Blomström-Lundqvist Renata Cífková Michele De Bonis Bernard Iung, et al. 2018 ESC Guidelines for the management of cardiovascular diseases during pregnancy. *European Heart Journal*, Volume 39, Issue 34, 7 September 2018, Pages 3165-3241.
23. Katriotis DG, Boriani G, Cosio FG, Hindricks G, Jais P, Josephson ME, Keegan R, Kim YH, Knight BP, Kuck KH, Lane DA, Lip GY, Malmberg H, Oral H, Pappone C, Themistoclakis S, Wood KA, Blomstrom-Lundqvist C. European Heart Rhythm Association (EHRA) consensus document on the management of supraventricular arrhythmias, endorsed by Heart Rhythm Society (HRS), Asia-Pacific Heart Rhythm Society (APHRS), and Sociedad Latinoamericana de Estimulación Cardíaca y Electrofisiología (SOLAECE). *Europace* 2017; 19: 465-511.
24. Kockova R, Kocka V, Kiernan T, Fahy GJ. Ibutilide-induced cardioversion of atrial fibrillation during pregnancy. *J Cardiovasc Electrophysiol* 2007; 18: 545-547.
25. Oishi M. L., Xing S. Atrial fibrillation: management strategies in the emergency department. *Emergency Medicine Practice*. 2013; 15 (2):1-28.
26. DeSilva R. A., Graboyes T. B., Podrid P. J., Lown B. Cardioversion and defibrillation. *American Heart Journal*. 1980; 100(6, part 1):881-895.
27. Sauvé N, Rey É, Cumyn A. Atrial fibrillation on a structurally normal heart in pregnancy: A case series and review of the literature. *J Obstet Gynaecol Can* 2017; 39: 18e24-18e24.
28. Gowda RM, Khan IA, Mehta NJ, Vasavada BC, Sacchi TJ. Cardiac arrhythmias in pregnancy: clinical and therapeutic considerations. *Int J Cardiol*. 2003 Apr; 88(2-3):129-33.
29. Gowda R., Punukollu G., Khan I., Wilbur S., Navarro V., Vasavada B., et al. (2003) Lone atrial fibrillation during pregnancy. *Int J Cardiol*: 123-124.
30. Bates S., Greer I., Middeldorp S., Veenstra D., Prabalos A., Vandvik P. (2012) VTE, thrombophilia, antithrombotic therapy, and pregnancy: Antithrombotic therapy and prevention of thrombosis, 9th ed: American College of Chest Physicians Evidence-Based Clinical Practice Guidelines. *Chest* 141(2 Suppl.): e691S-e736S.
31. Fuster V., Ryden L., Cannom D., Crijns H., Curtis A., Ellenbogen K., et al. (2006) ACC/AHA/ESC 2006 guidelines for the management of patients with atrial fibrillation: a report of the American College of Cardiology/American Heart Association Task Force on Practice Guidelines and the European Society of Cardiology Committee for Practice Guidelines (Writing Committee to revise the 2001 Guidelines for the Management of Patients With Atrial Fibrillation): developed in collaboration with the European Heart Rhythm Association and the Heart Rhythm Society. *Circulation* 114: e257-e354.
32. Walsh C., Manias T., Patient C. (2008) Atrial fibrillation in pregnancy. *Eur J Obstet Gynecol Reprod Biol*: 119-120.
33. RonPisters, Deirdre A.Lane, RobbyNieuwlaat, Cees B.de Vos, Harry J.G.M.Crijns, Gregory Y.H.Lipb. A Novel User-Friendly Score (HAS-BLED) To Assess 1-Year Risk of Major Bleeding in Patients with Atrial Fibrillation: The Euro Heart Survey. *Chest*. 2010 Nov; 138(5):1093-100.
34. Erküner Ö, Claessen R, Pisters R, Schulmer G, Ramaekers R, Sonneveld L, Dudink E, Lankveld T, Limantoro I, Weijs B, Pison L, Blaauw Y, de Vos CB, Crijns HJ. Poor anticoagulation relates to extended access times for cardioversion and is associated with long-term major cardiac and cerebrovascular events. *Int J Cardiol*. 2016 Dec 15; 225:337-341.
35. Dinh T, Baur LH, Pisters R, Kamp O, Verheugt FW, Smeets JL, Cheriex EC, Lindeboom JE, Heesen WF, Tieleman RG, Prins MH, Crijns HJ; TIARA investigators. Aspirin versus vitamin K antagonist treatment guided by transoesophageal echocardiography in patients with atrial fibrillation: a pilot study. *Heart*. 2014 Apr; 100(7):563-8.
36. Driver K, Chisholm CA, Darby AE, Malhotra R, Dimarco JP, Ferguson JD. Catheter ablation of arrhythmia during pregnancy. *J Cardiovasc Electrophysiol* 2015; 26:698-702.
37. Gras D, Mabo P, Kermarrec A, Bazin P, Varin C, Daubert C: Radiofrequency ablation of atrioventricular conduction during the 5th month of pregnancy. *Arch Mal Coeur Vaiss* 1992; 85:1873-1877.

38. Chen G, Sun G, Xu R, Chen X, Yang L, Bai Y, Yang S, Guo P, Zhang Y, Zhao C, Wang DW, Wang Y. Zero-fluoroscopy catheter ablation of severe drug-resistant arrhythmia guided by Ensite NavX system during pregnancy: Two case reports and literature review. *Medicine (Baltimore)* 2016; 95:e4487.
39. Kevin Driver, Christian A, Chisholm, Andrew E. Darby, Rohit M, J P Dimarco, J D Ferguson. Catheter Ablation of Arrhythmia During Pregnancy. *J Cardiovasc Electrophysiol*, Vol. 26, pp. 698-702, June 2015.
40. Bremme KA. Haemostatic changes in pregnancy. *Best Pract Res Clin Haematol*. 2003; 16:153–168.
41. Franchini M. Haemostasis and pregnancy. *Thromb Haemost*. 2006; 95: 401–413.
42. Rosenkranz A, Hiden M, Leschnik B, Weiss EC, Schlembach D, Lang U, Gallistl S, Muntean W. Calibrated automated thrombin generation in normal uncomplicated pregnancy. *Thromb Haemost*. 2008; 99: 331–337.
43. Goland S, Elkayam U. Anticoagulation in pregnancy. *Cardiol Clin*. 2012; 30: 395–405.
44. Granger JP, Alexander BT, Bennett WA, Khalil RA. Pathophysiology of pregnancy-induced hypertension. *Am J Hypertens*. 2001; 14: 178S–185S.
45. Ming-Sum Lee, Wansu Chen, Zilu Zhang, Lewei Duan, Angie Ng, Hillard T. Spencer, Damon M. Kwan, and Albert Y.-J. Shen, MD, MS. Atrial Fibrillation and Atrial Flutter in Pregnant Women—A Population-Based Study. *J Am Heart Assoc*. 2016 Apr; 5(4): e003182.
46. Link MS, Atkins DL, Passman RS, Halperin HR, Samson RA, White RD, Cudnik MT, Berg MD, Kudenchuk PJ, Kerber RE. Part 6: electrical therapies: automated external defibrillators, defibrillation, cardioversion, and pacing: 2010 American Heart Association guidelines for cardiopulmonary resuscitation and emergency cardiovascular care. *Circulation*. 2011; 123:e235.
47. Farida M. Jeejeebhoy , Carolyn M. Zelop , Steve Lipman , Brendan Carvalho , Jose Joglar , Jill M. Mhyre , Vern L. Katz , Stephen E. Lapinsky , Sharon Einav , Carole A. Warnes , Richard L. Page , Russell E. Griffin , Amish Jain , Katie N. Dainty , Julie Arafeh , Rory Windrim , Gideon Koren , and Clifton W. Callaway . and on behalf of the American Heart Association Emergency Cardiovascular Care Committee, Council on Cardiopulmonary, Critical Care, Perioperative and Resuscitation, Council on Cardiovascular Diseases in the Young, and Council on Clinical Cardiology. Cardiac Arrest in Pregnancy A Scientific Statement From the American Heart Association. *Circulation*. 2015;132:1747–1773.